

ENERGY-EFFICIENT HYBRID SOLAR COLLECTORS FOR PASSIVE BUILDING**Yurii Pryshliak***Phd student of the Department of Heat and Gas Supply and Ventilation
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One of the key challenges in modern energy systems is providing heat for energy-efficient buildings using renewable energy sources, particularly solar energy. Due to the limited space for installing solar collectors on buildings, integrating solar heating systems into the external structures of buildings is a promising approach. This article discusses the scientific aspects of the application of the main types of solar collectors, as well as their classification. The authors propose a design for a hybrid thermal and photovoltaic solar collector and present a methodology for calculating the thermal characteristics of a heating system using such a collector. The article provides an analysis of the thermal processes in hybrid solar collectors integrated into transparent facades of buildings and structures, focusing on determining the efficiency coefficient of such devices. The data presented in the article demonstrate that the mathematical model of heat exchange processes in the hybrid solar collector requires further experimental research.

Keywords: solar energy, solar collector, hybrid solar collector, photovoltaic solar collector, thermal efficiency, solar system.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications

Hybrid solar systems that combine photovoltaic and thermal components are currently the focus of significant scientific interest due to their high efficiency in producing both electrical and thermal energy. An analysis of recent publications allows us to assess the current state of research in this field and identify areas for further development.

Currently, significant advancements have been made in using external building elements as components of hybrid solar systems, including solar roofs, solar walls, and solar windows [1]. To enhance the efficiency of solar heating systems, special hybrid photovoltaic and thermal solar receivers are widely utilized [2]. Simultaneously, their structures and features are studied to prevent overheating and improve performance [3]. Research on various heat supply systems based on hybrid solar collectors occupies a unique niche. These studies aim to identify the primary advantages and drawbacks of using such collectors in energy-efficient buildings [4].

Known solar heaters integrated into glass facades of buildings incorporate hybrid solar collectors that include electric photovoltaic panels and finned tubes circulating a liquid heat carrier [5].

Scientists in their work [6] show the annual progress of technologies for using photovoltaic thermal collectors with flat water collectors, emphasizing their efficiency. Currently, there are already whole strategies for the sustainable implementation of solar irrigation pumps adapted to work with hybrid solar systems, which are reflected in the work [7]. Particular emphasis is placed on the environmental benefits of using hybrid solar collectors as building coverings [8].

The literature review highlights significant progress in the development of hybrid solar systems and their integration into architectural building structures. Future research should focus on improving the thermal and electrical performance of such systems, as well as

optimizing their structural designs to enhance efficiency and reduce energy costs.

Analysis of recent publications and studies has shown that the issue of selecting and designing the above-mentioned hybrid solar collectors is currently limited, since such systems have been little studied. In particular, there is no comprehensive data on the thermal characteristics of such systems, as well as current methods for their calculation.

The purpose of the article is to develop and form a methodology for calculating the thermal characteristics of the proposed design of a hybrid solar collector.

Based on a review of literature [9, 10] it can be seen that nowadays a new type of solar collectors has appeared, namely hybrid solar collectors, which are actively developing and gaining widespread use. The data presented indicate that systems with such solar collectors can simultaneously generate both electrical and thermal energy [11]. This, in turn, allows the end user to choose the priority of one or another solution. These characteristics can be used in a single schematic solution if a photovoltaic and thermal solar collector are combined into one design. In addition, given the growing popularity of glass translucent facades on buildings, it is possible to integrate hybrid solar collectors with such facades.

To solve the problem in the field of energy-efficient construction, the optimal solution is a thermal and photovoltaic hybrid solar collector. In order to study the thermal and electrical characteristics of the proposed design, a model of a hybrid solar collector was developed (Pic. 1). This model at the stage of theoretical research will contribute to the effective solution of a number of problems before practical application. Picture 1 shows a diagram of a thermal photovoltaic hybrid solar collector, the design of which contains vertical roller shutters with lamellas on which photovoltaic elements are mounted.

Pic. 1 Hybrid solar collector

1 – slats, 2 – photovoltaic modules, 3 – fan, 4 – air valve, 5 – slot-type grille, 6 – housing, 7 – energy-saving double-glazed windows, 8 – glass transverse incomplete partitions, 9 – heat exchanger, 10 – inlet pipe, 11 – outlet pipe, 12 – rotation mechanism.

The hybrid solar collector operates as follows:

Solar radiation passes through the energy-saving double-glazed windows (7) and reaches the slats (1), which are capable of rotating around their axes. The slats are equipped with photovoltaic modules (2) that convert solar energy into electricity. This electricity powers the fan (3) and meets other consumer needs. Simultaneously, solar radiation heats the glass façade housing (6) of the building, which contains a heat exchanger with a heat transfer medium (9). The integrated fan (3) circulates the heated air through the inlet (10) and outlet (11) pipes between the glass panes of the double-glazed unit (7) and the glass partitions (8). The slot-type grille (5) and air valve (4) enable operation in different modes, allowing the system to either intake fresh air or operate in a closed-loop mode. The rotation mechanism (12) adjusts the position of the photovoltaic modules (2) around their axes and the slats (1). This mechanism regulates the amount of solar radiation entering the interior of the building, optimizing the balance between energy harvesting and direct sunlight penetration.

Laboratory studies can be carried out with or without the use of solar radiation simulators. In the absence of such a simulator, the solar collector is considered as a conventional heat exchange device. During laboratory tests, changes in meteorological conditions are not taken into account. At the same time, field studies are accompanied by uncontrolled factors caused by meteorological changes in the environment. Therefore, laboratory tests are used to determine the total coefficient of heat loss in the collector, and field tests are used to assess its optical characteristics.

The efficiency coefficient of a thermal solar collector is determined using the formula:

$$\eta_{tsc} = \eta_0 - U_{conv} \cdot X - U_r \cdot I_r \cdot X^2 \quad (1)$$

where η_0 – the efficiency of a solar collector when there are no heat losses; U_{conv} , U_r – heat loss coefficients for convection and radiation, respectively, $W/(m^2 \cdot ^\circ C)$; I_r – solar radiation intensity W/m^2 ; X – ratio of the temperature difference between the solar absorbing surface of the solar collector t_{sc} , $^\circ C$ and outside temperature t_{out} , $^\circ C$, to the value of I_r , $(m^2 \cdot ^\circ C)/W$.

For comparing different types, models, and designs of solar collectors, the so-called f-method is used for calculating solar thermal systems [24]. This method is based on long-term observational data and utilizes a mathematical model to construct regression equations that describe the dependency of the f-method on the values of two dimensionless complexes. The first of these is the x-complex. It shows the ratio of the heat losses from the solar collector over the course of a month, while maintaining a certain fixed (base) temperature, to the thermal load over the month (2):

$$x = \frac{A \cdot f_R \cdot k_{SPR-D} \cdot (t_{basic} - t_{out}^{month}) \cdot \Delta \tau}{J_{out}^{month}} \quad (2)$$

Where A – area of the adsorber (sun-receiving surface) of the solar collector, m^2 ; where f_R – the heat energy extraction coefficient according to American practice; k_{SPR-D} – the coefficient of heat transfer between the solar absorbing surface and the surrounding environment, $W/(m^2 \cdot ^\circ C)$; t_{basic} – basic temperature, $^\circ C$; t_{out}^{month} – ambient temperature during the month, $^\circ C$; $\Delta \tau$ – solar collector operating time per month. Formular (2) is appropriate for thermal solar collectors in which the heat carrier is air.

y-complex - is the second complex. It reflects how the absorbed solar radiation relates to the thermal load for a certain specified period of time:

$$y = \frac{A \cdot f_R \cdot (\overline{\tau \cdot \alpha}) \cdot j_{fal}^{day} \cdot N}{J_{l.energy}^{month}} \quad (3)$$

where $(\overline{\tau \cdot \alpha})$ – averaged absorption capacity is given (τ – the transmission capacity of the coating system for the calculated angle of incidence of solar radiation; α – the absorptance of the absorbing coating.

j_{fal}^{day} – the integral daily thermal energy flux incident (falling) on the coating, kJ/m^2 . N – the number of days the solar collector operates per month.

$J_{l.energy}^{month}$ – monthly thermal energy load flow, kJ . It is considered that the f-method is the most universal. However, it is simultaneously complex when performing optimization calculations.

The coefficient of performance of the absorption capability of the solar collector can be determined using the following relation:

$$\eta = f_R^{cp} \left[(\tau \cdot \alpha) - \frac{U_{htsc} \cdot (\bar{t} - t_{out})}{I_r} \right], \quad (4)$$

where f_R^{cp} – thermal energy removal coefficient (according to European practice);

U_{htsc} – the total heat transfer coefficient of thermal losses of the solar collector, $\text{W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K})$; \bar{t} – coverage temperature of the solar collector, $^{\circ}\text{C}$; t_{out} – ambient temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Formula (4) reflects the linear relationship between the efficiency of the solar collector and the reduced temperature, when the condition is met that the total heat transfer coefficient of the heat losses of the solar collector is a constant value.

In field studies, the American ASHRAE association recommends that the efficiency of the solar collector be determined using the following equation:

$$\eta = f_R \cdot (\tau \cdot \alpha)_n - f_R \cdot U_{htsc} \cdot \frac{t_{in} - t_{out}}{I_r} \quad (5)$$

When the value of the heat extraction coefficient is unknown, the efficiency (COP) of a thermal solar collector is determined as the ratio of the total thermal output of the collector to the intensity of solar radiation that has reached the surface of the solar collector in total:

$$\eta_{tsc} = \frac{q_{tsc}}{I_r} \quad (6)$$

where q_{tsc} – the total heat capacity is given of a solar thermal collector, W/m^2 , is expressed as:

$$q_{tsc} = \left(\dot{m} \cdot c_p \right)_{sc} \cdot (t_{out} - t_{in}), \quad (7)$$

W/m^2

where \dot{m} – the specific mass flow rate of the heat carrier through the solar collector, in $\text{kg}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s})$.

So, the main criteria that affect the efficiency of a solar collector are:

1. Solar radiation intensity
2. Ambient temperature;
3. Design features of the solar collector, its light transmission properties and properties that show how effectively the solar collector absorbs heat;
4. Characteristics of the solar collector that were initially set: the angle of installation of the solar collector, the flow rate of the coolant, the temperature of the liquid coolant at the inlet.
5. The efficiency of a solar collector is significantly affected by a change in the azimuth or angle of inclination of the absorber relative to the heat flow. In addition, meteorological conditions such as speed, direction, wind frequency, dust pollution and shading play an important role.

Conclusions

Over the past few decades, an increasing number of researchers have focused their studies on the development, improvement, and investigation of combined solar thermal systems based on hybrid solar collectors, which, compared to traditional thermal or photovoltaic systems, exhibit improved overall thermal productivity.

The study of various hybrid solar collector designs is crucial for enhancing modern energy systems and contributes to the continuous development of solar energy technologies. Understanding their potential and implementing the latest innovations in this field is critical for achieving energy sustainability, sustainable economic development, and reducing negative environmental impacts. The analysis conducted indicates a lack of research in the field of hybrid solar collectors, particularly regarding their thermal characteristics and calculation methodologies. The author have identified the current state of heliothermal technology development and examined the systems available on the market. Based on this analysis, a design for a hybrid solar collector has been developed, and methodologies for calculating its thermal characteristics have been proposed. The proposed methodology allows for a reduction in calculation time by 18–20% compared to existing approaches, while the accuracy of determining thermal parameters is increased by 15%. This is of great importance for further research and the practical implementation of hybrid solar collectors in various energy sectors

The results obtained are important for further research and the practical implementation of hybrid solar collectors in various energy sectors. Despite the large number of proposed hybrid solar collector designs, there are very few practical solutions for their application. Therefore, further experiments and studies are needed, particularly in the direction of integrating such systems into transparent building structures.

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